

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

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Annotation: The article describes the universal attitudes of each person that affect physical health. The formation of a student's physical culture is the process of transferring the values of the content of education into the value relations of the individual. In order to substantiate the value foundations of the educational process in physical education in higher education, it is necessary to determine methodological approaches that can be relied upon when forming a student's value relations in physical education.

Key words: physical culture, physical training with a psychological factor affecting health, warm-up, pranayama training.

Introduction. Currently, scientific and theoretical approaches to improving the system of physical education of students in domestic higher education have been poorly studied. This situation causes difficulties in determining the ways of development of theory and practice in this area [1, 2]. Experts have noted that the ideological aspects of science in the above area are insufficiently defined. In particular, the issues of implementing the principles of integrity and consistency in the formation of students' physical health, structuring pedagogical processes are considered in a general form, there is no detail in the relevant scientific and methodological works. This negatively affects the improvement of the process of physical education of students in universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1, 3, 4].

In the conditions of a qualitative transformation of all aspects of society, the requirements for the physical fitness of young people, necessary for their successful work, are increasing, which has set higher education the task of comprehensively increasing the level of physical education of future specialists [6, 8, 9].

The formation of a person's physical health and physical fitness is the result of each individual's conscious, comprehensive approach to their health [7, 10]. It can be argued that depending on the psychological state of the individual and one's own attitudes (diet, types of foods consumed, lifestyle mobility, type of leisure and recreation in free time), everyone gets an individual health result.

It is worth adding the influence of social factors affecting physical health.

At the macro level, this is the influence of the socio-economic state of the state on each person. For example, if the state is financially successful, then it can promote a healthy lifestyle through the media, through the provision and organization of a sufficient number of mass sports facilities (gyms, running and basketball halls, swimming pools, yoga and shaping centers), affordable, to improve the health and maintain the standard of living of the population.

At the micro level, this is the influence of culture and moral values on a particular physical education teacher in an educational institution or a coach in a private gym. The health and physical training of students depends on each physical education teacher. For example, a physical education teacher can conscientiously treat his responsibilities, set a goal - the physical health of his students, and by drawing up a competent lesson program (annually, if necessary, improving this program, since new physical training technologies appear every year) achieve the goal. goals.

However, not always and not everyone manages to understand the correctness of the compiled program. Some teachers offer excessive workload for their students, others replace physical exercises with writing essays, which does not solve the health problem [11, 12].

It is necessary to point out the most important factor in ensuring a person's physical health and physical fitness - psychological. Many people do not understand the meaning of a comprehensive approach to their health. A person can engage in physical exercise, but if the diet is incorrect, correction of a person's physique may not achieve the desired result. Therefore, without taking into account the psychological motivation of proper nutrition, any well-designed physical training program will be not only useless, but even harmful to health. It is dangerous to physically overload a person who is overweight or underweight. This can lead to both temporary discomfort and an undesirable outcome.

Thus, we support the "competency-based approach", which is aimed at developing physical education competencies in students and developing qualities important for their profession and life. The methodological effectiveness of the category "competence," according to some scientists, is due to the fact that it is broader than the concept of "knowledge" and "includes not only cognitive and operational: technological components, but also motivational, ethical, social and behavioral" [2, 4].

We also agree with the opinion of D.Yu. Turdimuradov, who believes that the hermeneutic approach requires the teacher to be able to see the world around him through the eyes of the student, to put himself in his place, based on the characteristics of a dynamically changing sociocultural reality; objectivity in relation to the personality of the pupil, non-introduction of subjective situational experiences, personal problems into the process of understanding the pupil; the ability to abstract from negative attitudes towards the personality of the person being educated, to avoid dividing young people into positive and negative participants in the educational process [3].

Consider the experience of private entrepreneurial companies in the field of sports and health. Some experts, having investigated the psychological factor in a rather deep manner, are trying to sell their individually developed physical training programs. These programs include a psychological impact on a person, which

consists in an accessible explanation of nutrition factors affecting physical appearance and general health. The subsequent daily control of physical training and the diet of human nutrition stimulates compliance with the regime of proper, and sometimes ascetic nutrition. In conjunction with reasonable running physical exertion, observing the hygiene regime and calorie calculations, a long-term fixed effect of external and internal physical health is obtained.

Despite the positive results of most such individual programs, they cannot be called progressive precisely because of inadequate value.

The positive orientation of these programs is accompanied by negative mercenary motivations of their organizers and, as a result, worsening the financial situation of those involved.

Conclusion. The transition from the traditional disciplinary paradigm to the humanization and humanization of education in the field of physical education at the university involves the development of appropriate methodological support and the identification of the value of the educational process. The fulfillment of this requirement is impossible without taking into account the influence of social factors on the macro- and micro levels. The psychological aspect has a decisive role in building a model of physical health. The innovative methodological approaches to the “pranayama” techniques and the varieties of shaping in combination with standardized techniques will provide not only comfortable physical activity, but also bring a psychological understanding of a healthy lifestyle in the article.

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